

Fuzzy C-Means Clustering for Biomedical Documents using Ontology Based Indexing and Semantic Annotation

Authors : S.Logeswari, K.Premalatha

Abstract : Search is the most obvious application of Information retrieval. The variety of widely obtainable biomedical data is enormous and is expanding fast. This expansion makes the existing techniques are not enough to extract the most interesting patterns from the collection as per the user requirement. Recent researches are concentrating more on semantic based searching than the traditional term based searches. Algorithms for semantic searches are implemented based on the relations exist between the words of the documents. Ontologies are used as domain knowledge for identifying the semantic relations as well as to structure the data for effective information retrieval. Annotation of data with concepts of ontology is one of the wide-ranging practices for clustering the documents. In this paper, indexing based on concept and annotation are proposed for clustering the biomedical documents. Fuzzy c-means (FCM) clustering algorithm is used to cluster the documents. The performances of the proposed methods are analyzed with traditional term based clustering for PubMed articles in five different diseases communities. The experimental results show that the proposed methods outperform the term based fuzzy clustering.

Keywords : MeSH Ontology, Concept Indexing, Annotation, semantic relations, Fuzzy c-means

Conference Title : ICEP 2014 : International Conference on Electronic Publications

Conference Location : journal city, WASET

Conference Dates : November 23-23, 2014